

Advancing Bioeconomy Skills Development in Central Macedonia and Beyond

Policy Brief | Greek CoP

This policy brief outlines the key outcomes and recommendations from the Greek CoP's Regional Policy Workshop, held under the BioGov.net project, focusing on strategies to enhance bioeconomy skills development.

Introduction

The workshop's main outcomes and policy recommendations were generated through the collaborative efforts of the Greek CoP during the Regional Policy Workshop, held under the BioGov.net project.

This workshop, held on 14th March 2024, focused on identifying and addressing gaps in current governance systems and feedback loops to improve strategy design for bioeconomy skills development at multiple levels.

Being the culmination of the continuous efforts and hard work of the local CoP, the policy Workshop was the last out of a series of local CoP Meetings, resulting in tailored policy recommendations.

To achieve impact, the policy workshop was held in the context of the **Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival-Thessaloniki edition**, involving regional policy makers, academia, young people, and businesses with great bioeconomy innovation potential.

Bioeconomy in Central Macedonia at a glance

Regional Initiatives

01. European Strategic Framework for the Bioeconomy.
02. Greece's Circular Economy Action Plan (2021-2025).
03. Involvement of stakeholders like the Regional Development Fund (RDF), the Department of European Programs & Collaborations (DPCMC), and the Directorate of Environment, Industry, Energy, and Natural Resources.

Focus Areas

Emphasis on waste management and biogas utilisation, leading to sustainable resource utilisation, SME support, job creation, and improved living standards.

Skill gaps

Technical Skills, Digital Literacy, Networking and Cooperation, Project Management, Digital and Industrial Technologies, Local Bioeconomy Aspects, and Transversal skills.

Barriers and Obstacles to Bioeconomy Strategy Uptake

01. **Institutional Challenges**
 - Lack of a legal framework for secondary materials.
 - Uncoordinated actions and lack of legislative facilitation.
 - Inflexible policies and heavy bureaucracy.
02. **Implementation Challenges**
 - Absence of comprehensive statistics, complicating monitoring processes.
 - Minimal local citizen involvement in bioeconomy projects.
03. **Financial Challenges**
 - Insufficient funding for bioeconomy initiatives.
04. **Other Challenges**
 - Low green consumer awareness.
 - Poor cooperation culture between businesses.
 - Limited public knowledge about bioeconomy.
 - Difficulty engaging business community stakeholders and policymakers due to legislative jurisdiction by the central government and the dispersed nature of agrifood clusters.

Opportunities and Motivations after the Bioeconomy Strategy Uptake

01. **Promotion of Business Development**
 - Creation of new jobs.
02. **Research and Innovation Development**
 - Identification of specific demands.
 - Participation in European projects and Collaboration in R&D projects.
 - Establishment of alliances beyond the region.
03. **Policy Development and Empowerment of Existing Policy Frameworks**
 - Creation of new policy frameworks.
 - Establishment of funding schemes.
 - Development of critical infrastructures for bioeconomy initiatives.
04. **Awareness raising and Information Sharing**
 - Encouragement of stakeholders to align with bioeconomy principles.

Main takeaways and policy recommendations

Impact and Future Steps

The regional policy workshop held in Thessaloniki under the framework of the BioGov.net project successfully identified critical measures and strategies to enhance bioeconomy skills development in Greece.

In detail, concrete measures suggested by the local CoP for future bioeconomy uptake, are:

01. **Work Experience Programs**
 - Implement practical training for high school students before university.
 - Include hands-on training in various sectors, not just office environments.
02. **Tax Incentives for Education**
 - Provide tax benefits for citizens pursuing bioeconomy-related education.
03. **Certified Training Programs and Train the Trainers**
 - Map and certify trainers through universities.
 - Certify trainees attending lifelong learning programs in bioeconomy.
 - Organise regional programs to train educators on bioeconomy.
04. **Political Advocacy**
 - Advocate for incorporating bioeconomy into regional strategies.
05. **Smart KPI's**
 - Establish Key Performance Indicators for regional and educational evaluation.
06. **Observatories for Monitoring**
 - Create observatories to monitor local indicators.
 - Transfer methodological frameworks from universities to regional levels.
07. **Collaboration with Commerce Chambers**
 - Work with chambers of commerce on innovation plans.
 - Map businesses for potential financial incentives.
08. **Increased Funding**
 - Advocate for increased funding for technical education, especially in bioeconomy fields.
09. **Awareness Campaigns**
 - Raise awareness about bioeconomy at all educational levels.
10. **Educational Action Plans**
 - Develop and implement periodic educational action plans, including career days.

For more detailed information, visit the [Greek regions page](#) and [BioGov.net website](#).